

Landscape Management and Enhancing Landscape Values through Grazing

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Cattle grazing is an effective measure in creating a more open landscape in the Höytiäinen nature reserve on the shores of lake Pyhäselkä near the town of Joensuu in Eastern Finland. (Photo: Michael den Herder).

References

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Grazing in traditional rural biotopes such as semi-natural grasslands, wood pastures and heathland areas, has historically shaped rural landscapes in Finland. However, this practice has been in decline due to agricultural intensification and land abandonment. In *Finland*, special emphasis in landscape management by grazing is on restoring and managing traditional rural habitats such as coastal meadows, natural grasslands, wooded meadows and wood pastures, forest edges, and other semi-natural habitats.

Benefits of grazing in landscape management include 1) Biodiversity enhancement: Grazing helps preserve diverse plant species and habitats for wildlife. The selective feeding habits of livestock reduce the abundance of dominant plant species, promoting a mosaic of vegetation types that is beneficial for a wide range of insects, birds, and small mammals. 2) Soil health and carbon sequestration: Grazing improves soil structure and organic matter content. Livestock manure brings nutrients to soil and supports enhancing carbon sequestration in soils, which is key for mitigating climate change. 3) Reduction of invasive species: Grazing is an effective, low-impact tool to control invasive species that threaten native ecosystems, reducing the need for chemical herbicides and weeding. 4) Cultural landscape conservation: Grazing maintains and preserves open landscapes that are culturally and historically significant as traditional Finnish agricultural landscapes.

Landscape grazing enhances the landscape values which could not be restored without animals. Farmers and land managers can optimize grazing by adjusting stocking rates, grazing seasons, and livestock species according to the local ecosystem. Farmers can also benefit from new business activities compatible with landscape management such as rural tourism and direct sales of meat. The Grazing Bank (<https://www.laidunpankki.fi/>) is an open online marketplace connecting animal owners and landowners aiming at increasing contract-based collaborations in landscape grazing in *Finland*.

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